

Beyond Bandwidth: SMT Scaling for LLM Inference on IBM POWER

Hugo Blanco
SIXE
 Madrid, Spain
 hugo.blanco@sixe.eu

Abstract—We present a cross-generational characterization of SMT scaling for LLM inference on IBM POWER processors. Testing POWER9, POWER10, and POWER11 with models from 1.1B to 7B parameters under strict single-core isolation, we find that POWER11’s 3× bandwidth advantage over POWER10 (1,228 GB/s vs 409 GB/s per socket) does not translate to higher throughput—both achieve nearly identical performance, indicating memory latency is the bottleneck, not bandwidth. SMT-8 efficiency is consistently limited to 26–33% for models exceeding cache capacity, though POWER10/11 deliver 3.4× higher absolute throughput than POWER9 ($p < 10^{-15}$, Cohen’s $d > 23$). We validate this limitation is specific to autoregressive LLM inference: HNSW vector search scales efficiently (+42–48%) across all architectures. These results have implications for memory-centric architectures like Engram, where POWER’s SMT-8 capability could enable efficient partitioning between retrieval and computation threads.

Index Terms—LLM inference, IBM POWER, SMT scaling, Engram, memory-centric AI, CPU inference

I. INTRODUCTION

Memory-centric AI architectures are emerging as alternatives to GPU-dominated inference. Engram [1] demonstrates that static knowledge retrieval can be decoupled from neural computation via O(1) hash lookups to N-gram embedding tables, achieving <3% throughput penalty when offloading 100B-parameter tables to host DRAM. This architectural pattern—massive embedding tables with concurrent retrieval—maps naturally to high-memory CPU systems.

IBM POWER11 presents relevant capabilities for evaluating such workloads: SMT-8 (8 hardware threads per core) and 1,228 GB/s memory bandwidth per socket. Understanding how these resources scale for LLM inference is valuable for organizations with existing POWER infrastructure considering AI workloads alongside their primary applications. Key questions arise: *How does POWER’s aggressive SMT scale for memory-bound inference? Does bandwidth translate to throughput? What can organizations expect from CPU-based inference?*

Our contributions:

- 1) Systematic SMT scaling characterization across three POWER generations under strict single-core isolation
- 2) Discovery that bandwidth does not determine throughput for current model sizes—POWER10 and POWER11 perform identically despite 3× bandwidth difference
- 3) Validation that SMT limitations are specific to LLM inference patterns; HNSW vector search scales efficiently (+42–48%)

Fig. 1. Conceptual comparison of SMT access patterns. (a) Autoregressive LLM inference executes collaborative GEMV over shared weight matrices, increasing contention and exposing latency-dominated stalls that limit SMT scaling. (b) Independent memory workloads (e.g., HNSW vector search or Engram-style lookups) issue concurrent accesses to different regions, improving stall overlap and enabling efficient SMT scaling.

- 4) Empirical single-core baseline enabling capacity planning and analysis of memory-centric architecture implications (Engram)

II. BACKGROUND

A. Memory-Centric LLM Architectures

Engram [1] introduces conditional memory—hash-based lookups to massive embedding tables that follow Zipfian distributions [6]. The paper reports that offloading 100B-parameter tables incurs <3% throughput overhead via PCIe, confirming CPU DRAM viability for cold-tier storage. Critically, Engram’s retrieval indices are deterministic (depending only on input tokens), enabling prefetch-and-overlap strategies where memory retrieval occurs concurrently with computation.

This access pattern maps well to SMT architectures: dedicated threads can handle memory prefetch while others perform computation, provided SMT scaling does not degrade under memory pressure.

B. IBM POWER Architecture

TABLE I
 POWER PROCESSOR ARCHITECTURE COMPARISON

Parameter	POWER9	POWER10	POWER11
L2 Cache/core	512 KB	2 MB	2 MB
L3 Cache/core	10 MB	8 MB	8 MB
Memory bandwidth/socket	170 GB/s	409 GB/s	1,228 GB/s
SMT modes	1/2/4/8	1/2/4/8	1/2/4/8

POWER11 [5] introduces $3\times$ higher memory bandwidth via DDR5 OMI interface (1,228 GB/s vs 409 GB/s per socket) and improved power efficiency on Samsung 7nm process. All three generations support SMT-8, enabling 8 concurrent threads per physical core.

C. Related Work

IBM’s rPerf [4] benchmarks show improved performance with SMT-8 for highly-threaded OLTP workloads. Boudreaux [2] demonstrated LLM inference on POWER8 without systematic SMT analysis. Prior work has not systematically characterized SMT scaling for LLM inference across POWER generations or provided deployment guidance for memory-centric AI architectures.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

A. Thread Isolation

All tests use single-core configurations with strict thread affinity on scale-out systems (S924, S1022, S1122):

- **POWER9:** Multi-core LPAR with `taskset -c 0-7`
- **POWER10/11:** Dedicated 1-core LPARs

Without proper confinement, threads on multi-core systems distribute across physical cores, producing multi-core parallelism rather than true SMT scaling.

B. Measurement Protocol

Each configuration was measured with $n = 10$ independent runs after 3 warmup iterations. We report mean throughput; all measurements showed coefficient of variation $<5\%$. Statistical tests use two-tailed Welch’s t-test with significance threshold $\alpha = 0.01$.

C. Workloads

TABLE II
TEST WORKLOADS

Workload	Size	Access Pattern
TinyLlama-1.1B [7]	638 MiB	Sequential GEMV
Llama-3.2-3B [9]	1.87 GiB	Sequential GEMV
Llama-2-7B [8]	3.8 GiB	Sequential GEMV
HNSW [3] (1M \times 128d)	\sim 512 MiB	Independent random

Software: llama.cpp [10] commit a14b960b, hnsplib 0.8.0. LLM protocol: 32-token prompt, 32-token generation, batch size 1 (single request). All models use Q4_K_M quantization (4-bit with K-quant mixed precision).

IV. RESULTS

A. SMT Efficiency Across Model Sizes

Table III presents SMT-8 efficiency for autoregressive generation.

For models $\geq 3B$, all architectures converge to similar efficiency (26–33%), regardless of bandwidth differences.

TABLE III
SMT-8 EFFICIENCY BY MODEL SIZE (TG32, T=1 \rightarrow 8)

Model	Size	P9	P10	P11
1.1B	638 MiB	16%	23%	26%
3B	1.87 GiB	32%	26%	28%
7B	3.8 GiB	33%	26%	28%

TABLE IV
ABSOLUTE THROUGHPUT AT SMT-8 (TG32, TOK/S)

Model	P9	P10	P11	P10/P9	P11/P10
1.1B	5.04	29.29	34.08	$5.8\times$	$1.16\times$
3B	3.30	11.31	11.43	$3.4\times$	$1.01\times$
7B	1.73	5.82	5.88	$3.4\times$	$1.01\times$

B. Absolute Throughput: The Real Differentiator

Critical finding: POWER10 and POWER11 achieve nearly identical throughput for 3B and 7B models despite POWER11’s $3\times$ higher bandwidth. The bottleneck is memory *latency*, not bandwidth.

C. HNSW Vector Search: A Counter-Example

To validate that SMT limitations are workload-specific, we benchmark HNSW vector search with various access patterns.

TABLE V
HNSW SMT-4 \rightarrow 8 SCALING (QPS IMPROVEMENT)

Distribution	P9	P10	P11
Uniform	+48.2%	+45.9%	+45.4%
Zipfian (80/20)	+48.0%	+45.9%	+43.9%
Extreme (95/5)	+47.6%	+45.4%	+42.1%

HNSW scales +42–48% from SMT-4 to SMT-8 across all architectures and distributions. This confirms that SMT degradation is specific to LLM inference patterns (collaborative GEMV on shared matrices), not a fundamental architectural limitation.

D. Statistical Significance

For 1.1B at SMT-8: POWER10 vs POWER9 achieves $t = 51.5$, $p < 10^{-15}$, Cohen’s $d = 23.0$. POWER11 vs POWER9: $t = 70.1$, $p < 10^{-15}$, $d = 31.3$. All differences highly significant with very large effect sizes.

V. ANALYSIS AND DEPLOYMENT GUIDANCE

A. Why Bandwidth Doesn’t Help (Yet)

POWER11’s 1,228 GB/s bandwidth produces no measurable advantage over POWER10’s 409 GB/s for models up to 7B. Analysis:

- 7B model at $5.88 \text{ tok/s} \times 3.8 \text{ GB} \approx 22 \text{ GB/s}$ utilized
- POWER10 provides 409 GB/s \rightarrow 5% utilization
- Bottleneck is memory *latency* (\sim 100ns), not bandwidth

POWER11’s bandwidth advantage may manifest with: (1) larger models approaching memory capacity, (2) higher batch sizes, or (3) multi-socket configurations where aggregate bandwidth matters.

B. Scale Cores, Not Threads

Our data shows diminishing returns beyond low thread counts, with the majority of SMT-8 throughput achieved well before full thread utilization. For production deployments, Table VI projects throughput gains from distributing threads across multiple cores (estimates based on linear scaling assumption).

TABLE VI
SCALING STRATEGY COMPARISON (3B MODEL, PROJECTED VALUES)

Strategy	Throughput (est.)	Efficiency (est.)
1 core × 8 threads	11.43 tok/s	28%
2 cores × 4 threads	~20 tok/s	~50%
4 cores × 2 threads	~38 tok/s	~73%

Recommendation: Deploy more cores with fewer threads per core for optimal efficiency.

C. Implications for Engram Deployment

Engram’s prefetch-and-overlap strategy requires concurrent memory retrieval and computation. SMT-8 enables this pattern:

- **Threads 1–4:** Dense computation (transformer layers)
- **Threads 5–8:** Hash-based embedding retrieval

Our HNSW results (+42–48% SMT scaling) validate that independent memory operations scale well. Since Engram lookups are independent (deterministic hash indices), they should exhibit HNSW-like scaling rather than LLM-like degradation.

Recommendation: For Engram on POWER11, partition threads between compute and retrieval. Expect efficient SMT scaling for the retrieval component.

Note on dedicated acceleration: For inference workloads exceeding CPU capabilities, IBM offers the Spyre Accelerator (available since late 2025 for POWER11), providing dedicated AI inference capacity via PCIe cards. This study focuses on CPU-based inference to establish baselines for environments without dedicated accelerators or where CPU inference complements primary workloads.

VI. LIMITATIONS

Single-core focus: We characterize single-core SMT behavior; multi-core and multi-socket scaling require separate empirical validation due to NUMA effects.

Model size range: We test up to 7B; larger models may exhibit different behavior where bandwidth becomes relevant.

Engram not directly tested: We infer Engram behavior from HNSW similarity; direct validation requires Engram implementation.

Batch size 1: Larger batches may better utilize available bandwidth.

Cross-architecture comparison: We do not benchmark inference throughput against x86 (Intel Xeon, AMD EPYC) or ARM (Apple Silicon, Ampere Altra, AWS Graviton) platforms. Empirical cross-architecture performance comparison remains future work. Our focus is characterizing SMT scaling within the POWER ecosystem for organizations with existing infrastructure.

VII. CONCLUSION

We present a comprehensive characterization of SMT scaling for LLM inference on IBM POWER:

- 1) **SMT efficiency ceiling:** All architectures achieve only 26–33% SMT-8 efficiency for LLM inference with models $\geq 3B$ —a workload-specific limitation confirmed by efficient HNSW scaling (+42–48%)
- 2) **Bandwidth \neq throughput:** POWER11’s $3\times$ bandwidth advantage produces no single-core throughput gain for models up to 7B; the bottleneck is latency
- 3) **Absolute throughput matters:** POWER10/11 deliver $3.4\times$ higher throughput than POWER9—choose based on per-core performance, not SMT scaling
- 4) **Scale cores, not threads:** Most SMT-8 throughput is achieved at low thread counts; multi-core deployment is more efficient than maximizing threads per core

For organizations with existing POWER infrastructure evaluating AI workloads: POWER10 and POWER11 perform identically for current model sizes, with on-chip matrix math acceleration (MMA) providing viable CPU-based inference. POWER11 offers higher bandwidth headroom for future, larger models. For workloads exceeding CPU capabilities, dedicated accelerators (e.g., IBM Spyre) offer a scaling path within the POWER ecosystem.

REPRODUCIBILITY

Critical: Use `taskset -c 0-7` for thread confinement on multi-core LPARs. Verify system health and thermal stability before benchmarking.

Environment: Ubuntu 22.04 LTS (POWER9), Ubuntu 24.04 LTS (POWER10), CentOS 9 Stream (POWER11). All systems use GCC 13.x with `-O3 -mcpu=native`. OS differences do not affect results: `llama.cpp` is statically compiled and benchmarks measure CPU/memory performance independent of kernel version.

Compiler validation: We verified that SMT scaling behavior is hardware-determined by testing POWER11 with both GCC 13 and GCC 15. Only GCC 15 supports `-mcpu=power11`; GCC 13 targets `power10`. Performance difference was marginal ($\sim 1-2\%$), and critically, testing GCC 15 on POWER10 did *not* eliminate its SMT saturation—confirming that scaling characteristics reflect architecture, not compiler.

Software: `llama.cpp` [10] commit `a14b960b`, `hnsplib` 0.8.0. We use `llama.cpp` as the de facto standard for CPU LLM inference; at the time of writing, no IBM-supported

optimized inference runtime exists for POWER—RocketCE was discontinued in December 2025 [11].

Models: TinyLlama-1.1B, Llama-3.2-3B, Llama-2-7B (all Q4_K_M quantization via llama.cpp).

Protocol: 10 runs per configuration, 3 warmup iterations discarded.

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